

lasted 5 min at 72 °C. The PCR products were visualized on a 1 % agarose gel run in 0.5 × TBE buffer and stained with ethidium bromide. The figure reveals amplifications of the expected size and they were identical to the DNA isolated using a standard method. DNA preparations from both the monoconidial isolates of B157 amplified the desired product, indicating reproducibility.

The yield of DNA using this method was 0.5-1.0 µg from a small sample of mycelia, which is sufficient to carry out a number of PCR and randomly amplified polymorphic DNA reactions. Employing this method of DNA extraction, we have been able to extract DNA of good quality from other filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Phytium*, *Rhizoctonia*, and *Sclerotirzia*) that confirm its general applicability. ■

Method for detecting rice sheath blight pathogen in soil samples using mungbean

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This technique uses mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) as a bait plant to detect propagules of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn, a soilborne fungus that causes rice sheath blight. The technique involves the collection of soil samples from the field, with each sample consisting of 300-350 g (Fig. 1). Each sample is placed in pots (11 cm diam × 16 cm height) with holes for draining, and each pot filled with soil is placed inside a clean plastic bag to avoid contamination among samples during transport. Soil samples are air-dried for 10 d at 30-33 °C. Extreme temperatures, above 37-40 °C, which cause destruction of soil organisms, must be avoided. After drying to a soil moisture content of about 17-21% (w/w), each sample is then pounded to a particle size of approximately 2-5 mm in diameter and

1. Methodology for detecting *R. solani* pathogenic to rice in soil samples using mungbean seedlings.

dispensed in the original pots. Mungbean observations are done at 2- to 3-d intervals for 15 d, starting 4 d after sowing, of number of healthy plants, diseased plants, and ungerminated seeds in each pot. Seedlings infected with *R. solani* have dark brown lesions on the hypocotyl and/or cotyledons. A seedling is considered emerged when its cotyledon appears above the soil surface. Stems of infected seedlings that are more than 7 d old have dark brown lesions near the soil surface. Infected mungbean are soaked for 15 s in 5%

calcium hypochlorite, and infected tissues are cut into small sections and placed on petri dishes with potato dextrose agar (PDA) with 1 ml L⁻¹ of 25% lactic acid. After 2 d, *R. solani* colonies are again plated on PDA. Three 8-mm leaf cuts obtained from third or fourth leaves of 40- to 50-d-old IR72 are placed on water agar (0.5 g agar L⁻¹ distilled water). About 8 mm of a 4- to 5-d-old mycelial plug is placed on the center of each leaf section and incubated at 25-27 °C for 4 d to detect lesions.

2. Proportion of true positive and false positive samples using the presence of infected seedlings as criterion (a) and the proportion of false negative and true negative samples using two successive criteria: presence of infected seedlings and presence of *R. solani*-like colonies on ungerminated seeds (b).

Figure 2 shows the proportion of false positives and false negatives from a large series of samples. Criterion is based on the isolation of *R. solani*-like colonies on ungerminated seeds. There were 37.5% false negatives using the first criterion (presence of infected seedlings), while the proportion of false negatives was reduced to 16.0% using the second criterion in sequence (presence of *R. solani*-like fungus colonizing ungerminated seeds).

When the second criterion alone is considered, low contamination of a soil sample leads to very few false positives (1 and 3, respectively, for IRRI and Pila soils). However, this test leads to relatively high false negative cases (28 and 16, respectively, for IRRI and Pila soils). Nevertheless, c^2 values (19.7 for IRRI and 28.7 for Pila) indicate that this test adequately detects colonization of soil samples by *R. solani*. ■

DNA fingerprinting of bacterial blight pathogen directly from infected leaves

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In this study, we shortened the time required to obtain DNA fingerprints by using pathogen DNA prepared directly from cells leached from infected leaves. Leaves of IR24 plants grown in the greenhouse were inoculated (clip method) with six isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* belonging to different lineages, and infected leaves were collected 14 d later. To 'ooze' bacteria from the leaves, 2-cm-long leaf fragments containing the advancing tip of lesions were cut crosswise into 10 small pieces with flame-sterilized scissors, and then soaked in 400 μ L of sterile distilled water for at least 1 h. The leaf pieces were discarded and the cells concentrated by spinning the suspension for 2 min in a microcentrifuge. Most of the water was discarded, leaving about 25 μ L, in which the cells were resuspended. The cells were lysed in 200 μ L of 70% ethanol (final concentration) and then spun for 10 s to pellet the cell debris. The supernatant was transferred to a new tube and spun for 5 min to precipitate DNA. The DNA was air-dried, dissolved in 10 μ L of sterile water and 5 μ L served as template for polymerase chain reaction (PCR). To check the consistency of the fingerprint patterns, purified DNA from the isolates used for inoculation served as positive controls. Standard PCR protocols were followed using JEL1 /JEL2 primers and with the repPCR primers BOX, ERIC, and REP using DNA from bacterial exudates from lesions and using DNA from cultured cells.

Figure 1 compares the fingerprint patterns from the alcohol lysis method to those obtained using DNA prepared by the potassium acetate method. The latter has a smeary background that obscured some bands, apparently from residual chemical contaminants. When intact cells were used directly in the PCR reaction, the results were incon-